

SVETLANA LUNINA, AN UZBEK WOMAN WHO CONTRIBUTED TO THE FIELD OF ARCHEOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13894546>

Annotation: This article talks about the life and work of Svetlana Lunina, an Uzbek woman who contributed to the field of archaeology.

Keywords: Tirnama is ceramic, Altintepa, Marv, brass, mirror, terracotta.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada arxeologiya sohasiga o'z xissasini qo'shgan o'zbek ayoli Svetlana Luninaning hayoti va ijodi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tirnama sopol, Oltintepa, Marv, jez, ko'zgu, terrakota.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается о жизни и творчестве Светланы Луниной, узбекчи, внесшей вклад в область археологии.

Ключевые слова: Я царапаю керамику, Алтынтепа, Марв, латунь, зеркало, terrakota.

Archeology is a science that studies the past of human society based on the monuments of ancient material culture. The 19th century was a period of great archaeological discoveries, and it began to take shape as a science. In 1895, the Archeology amateur club was established. Among the archeological scientists such as Yakhyo Gulomov, Akhmadali Askarov, Abdulkhamid Anorboev, women scientists such as Zamira Usmonova, Svetlana Lunina, Tamara Pushkina have participated in search and excavation work for several years and have become famous experts in their field.

The German historian E. Ceren is quoted as saying: "There is rarely a more depressing profession than that of the field archaeologist, who works in the desert, among wild rocks, completely far from any civilization, in harsh climates that deprive a person of courage... the most knowledgeable of all are archaeologists. They will continue to work as if their working conditions were taken for granted. For them, there is no profession in the whole world that is more interesting than the one they have chosen. They live in danger, with a secret that has yet to be revealed. If not today, it will be revealed tomorrow or later, and the press will recognize their names". One of them is our hero.

Svetlana Borisovna Lunina, Uzbek archaeologist, professor of Tashkent State University, who conducted research on painting techniques and ceramic materials of Central Asian monuments, was born on October 7, 1932 in Tashkent. After finishing school, he was recommended to study at the Faculty of History of the State University of Central Asia. In 1955, he studied at the Faculty

of History and Archaeology. From 1955 to 1958, Svetlana studied at the Faculty of Archeology under the supervision of Mikhail Masson and Galina Pugachenkova. From 1968 to 1981, he worked as the head of the archeology department. In 1968, after collecting materials during the South Turkmenistan Archaeological Complex (YuTAKE) expedition, he defended his dissertation on pottery in the city of Marv [1. P – 108]. In 1981-1984, he worked as an associate professor of the history department. He teaches various aspects of Central Asian archeology from historical, archaeological and visual perspectives. In cooperation with the Department of Geology, he organizes art history and theory courses in the city of Samarkand. In addition, he established a laboratory of stratigraphy of Quaternary sediments and ancient deposits of Uzbekistan in the city of Samarkand. In 1990, he was awarded the title of professor. More than 150 scientific works have been published in journals in Uzbekistan, as well as in St. Petersburg, Moscow, Ashgabat, Austria and France.

In the early sixties, Svetlana Lunina organizes expeditions in excavations in Marv and around Tashkent (Nogaykurgan, Kogaytepa, Mingtepa cemeteries). In 1964, he participated in the Kashkadarya expedition, and in 1968-1981 he was its leader. The Oltintepa city ruins consisted of two parts: the central part, which played the role of a fortress, and the outer part. A lot of glazed ceramic vessels decorated with various patterns and inscriptions, coins, terracotta fragments, brass, mirrors, ashtrays, figurines and others were found here. In front of the pottery kilns, 31 coins minted by Arslan Khan and Ibrahim from the Karakhanids were also found in 1179-1180. The discovery of these coins made it possible to get acquainted with the period of the 12th-13th centuries. A city cemetery dating back to the 10th-11th centuries was also found and studied in the Altintepa area. No items or jewelry were placed in front of the corpse [2. P – 34]. In 1966, together with N. I. Krasheninkova, he conducted small research in the Kashkadarya detachment. According to researches, it was determined that the city consists of three parts: the arch, the city, and the suburbs. Many hills of different sizes have been found in the territory of Shakhristan, and the remains of old buildings are hidden under them. The small rectangular area of the city, located at an average height of 4.3 m above the rest of the city area, aroused great interest. In 1967, Z. I. Usmonova visited the exploration works in Altintep. The group gathers, collects materials, and cleans the remains of mosque buildings, which are carved and decorated with objects [3. P – 31].

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS OF THE SCIENTIST:

1. 1955: Sealed decorative bowl from Tali-Barzu;

2. 1959: The potters' quarter in the western part of Marv;
3. 1967: Qizbibi Mausoleum. Monument of Turkmenistan;
4. 1972: Kashkadarya expedition;
5. 1978: Musical instrument from Altintep.

Several other similar works have also been published.

In conclusion, it should be said that the task of the science of archeology is to restore our ancient history through the material culture monuments of the primitive, ancient and medieval periods of human society. Svetlana Lunina studied the monuments of the Middle Ages and left valuable information for the future youth. Above, we only talked about the scientist's achievements and published articles, but it is not easy to imagine how hard he achieved this victory

References:

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3. Лунина С. Города южного Согда в VIII–XII вв. – Т. “Фан” – 1984. С – 150.
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